

Synthesis, magnetic and spectral studies of copper(II) complexes of 2-substituted benzaldehyde semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : Some complexes of divalent copper have been synthesized by refluxing the metal salts with the ligands 2-chlorobenzaldehyde semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone (cbsc, cbtsc) and 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone (ebsc, ebtsc). All these complexes are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR and electronic spectral studies. IR spectral data of the complexes reveals bidentate complexing nature of the ligands coordinating through oxygen atom of carbonyl group/sulphur atom of thioketo form and azomethine nitrogen atom. High spin configuration has been indicated by magnetic moment of the complexes. For all the metal complexes the probable structures are also reported here.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazone, copper(II), synthesis, benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone.

Introduction

The chemistry of the transition metal complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones have been receiving considerable attention largely because of their wide synthetic and analytical applications as well as biological activities¹. In recent years thiosemicarbazones have been evaluated for the analytical determination of metals². Occurrence of copper(II) in human body as also in other living beings and plants in the form of cuproprotein is known since long³. It is interesting to note that catalytic activity of cuproprotein is about thousand times as great as that of equivalent amount of cupric ions⁴. In the present study, we report the synthesis of complexes of divalent copper with the ligands 2-chlorobenzaldehyde semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone (cbsc, cbtsc) and 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone (ebsc, ebtsc), magnetic and spectral studies of these complexes on the basis of various physico-chemical techniques.

Results and discussion

Synthesized metal complexes were insoluble in water and most of the organic solvents with the exception of polar solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The analytical data of all the complexes correspond to 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometric ratio indicating coordination of anions and have the general formula CuL_2X_2 (L \rightarrow cbsc, ebsc, cbtsc and ebtsc, X \rightarrow Cl^- , Br^- , CH_3COO^- and $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$). The complexes exhibit different stereo-chemistry varying from

four coordinated tetrahedral, five coordinated square pyramidal and trigonal bipyramidal and six coordinated octahedral.

IR spectral studies :

The main vibrational bands (cm^{-1}) of the ligands and complexes are reported. The ligands show main absorption bands in the region $\sim 3015-3030\ cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu(C-H)$, $\sim 1610\ cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu(C=C)$, $745-760\ cm^{-1}$ (*ortho* substitution) diagnostic of aromatic character⁵. The strong bands at $\sim 1660\ cm^{-1}$ and $\sim 1532\ cm^{-1}$ are assignable to $\nu(C=O)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ stretching vibrations⁶ respectively. The bands in the region $3370-3125\ cm^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu(NH)$ and $\nu(NH_2)$ stretching vibrations⁷ of free ligand and remain practically unchanged or shift slightly to higher side indicating no coordination. The medium intensity bands occur at $\sim 815\ cm^{-1}$ for $\nu(C=S)$ ⁶ and $\sim 995-1000\ cm^{-1}$ for $\nu(N-N)$ vibrations⁸ respectively but the former shifts to lower side suggesting the sulphur atom is taken part in coordination with metal ion. The absence of the bands above $3400\ cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu(O-H)$ or in the region $2500-2600\ cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu(S-H)$ vibrations suggests the presence of ligands in the keto/thione form⁹ respectively.

The shifting of characteristic bands of free ligands in the complex indicates the bidentate behaviour of the ligands in all the complexes. The strong bands observed at $\sim 1660\ cm^{-1}$ and $\sim 1532\ cm^{-1}$ are affected upon coordination and shift to lower side by $\sim 20-50\ cm^{-1}$ and $\sim 30-55$

cm^{-1} respectively in all the complexes, which suggest the involvement of oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atom in coordination with metal ion. In the acetato complexes $\nu_a(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$ are observed at 1660 cm^{-1} and 1438 cm^{-1} respectively indicating bridging nature of the acetate ion as the separation between two frequencies is much larger in unidentate complexes than in the free ion¹⁰. The IR spectral data of sulphato complexes exhibit bands at $1094\text{--}1123 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 954\text{--}958 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding monodentate behaviour of sulphate group¹¹.

are absent in present case¹⁵. All the semicarbazone complexes except sulphato may be assigned to have tetragonal structure in planar configuration of the two semicarbazone molecules around metal ion with the anions occupying axial positions as the results resemble to that of semicarbazide chloro complex of copper(II) for which crystal structure is known¹⁶.

The electronic spectra of complexes reported here except sulphato complexes exhibit only a broad absorp-

Table 1. Elemental analysis data of copper(II) complexes

Complexes	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
		Cu	C	H	N
Cu(ebsc) ₂ Cl ₂	Blue	11.65 (11.59)	43.79 (43.75)	4.83 (4.74)	15.28 (15.31)
Cu(ebsc) ₂ Br ₂	Bluish green	10.00 (9.97)	37.57 (37.64)	4.19 (4.08)	13.27 (13.18)
Cu(ebsc) ₂ SO ₄	Bluish green	11.00 (11.08)	41.96 (41.84)	4.48 (4.53)	14.67 (14.65)
Cu(ebsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Brown	10.58 (10.67)	48.24 (48.36)	5.30 (5.37)	14.20 (14.10)
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	Dull brown	11.02 (10.95)	41.40 (41.34)	4.37 (4.48)	14.41 (14.47)
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ Br ₂	Greenish blue	9.51 (9.49)	35.90 (35.84)	3.77 (3.88)	12.48 (12.55)
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ SO ₄	Light green	10.38 (10.49)	39.59 (39.36)	4.39 (4.29)	13.84 (13.87)
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Brown	10.22 (10.13)	46.00 (45.89)	5.17 (5.10)	13.43 (13.39)
Cu(cbse) ₂ Cl ₂	Green	11.95 (12.00)	36.34 (36.26)	3.11 (3.02)	15.91 (15.86)
Cu(cbse) ₂ Br ₂	Greenish black	10.33 (10.27)	31.00 (31.04)	2.68 (2.59)	13.56 (13.58)
Cu(cbse) ₂ SO ₄	Light green	11.60 (11.65)	35.27 (35.19)	3.00 (2.93)	15.47 (15.40)
Cu(cbse) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Brownish green	11.14 (11.02)	41.57 (41.63)	3.89 (3.81)	14.50 (14.57)
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	Orange	11.29 (11.32)	34.26 (34.19)	3.00 (2.85)	15.00 (14.96)
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ Br ₂	Red black	9.90 (9.77)	29.40 (29.51)	2.49 (2.46)	13.00 (12.91)
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ SO ₄	Reddish brown	10.80 (10.83)	32.86 (32.73)	2.67 (2.73)	14.40 (14.32)
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Dark red	10.53 (10.44)	39.50 (39.44)	3.77 (3.62)	13.84 (13.80)

Study of magnetic moment and electronic spectral bands :

The observed magnetic moments at room temperature for divalent copper complexes are in the range 1.74–2.10 B.M. (Table 2) corresponding to one unpaired electron around the metal ion¹² with the only exception being acetate complexes of semicarbazones (cbse, 1.59 B.M. and ebsc, 1.57 B.M.) indicating polymeric structure for complexes. Irrespective of the stereochemistry involved, bivalent copper complexes contain one unpaired spin¹³ per copper atom. So, there should be some correlation between the magnitude of orbital contribution and coordination geometry. Lower magnetic moment or even diamagnetism results¹⁴ to antiferromagnetic interactions which

tion band ranging $13375\text{--}15900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a well defined shoulder in the range $15430\text{--}18200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). These spectral bands may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively. The low intensity bands due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ is usually not observed as a separate band in an octahedral field^{17,18}. The splitting of the 2E_g state is a measure of the planar and axial fields. The change of position of the bands would be due to axial field only. Electronic spectra of these complexes were found to have tetragonal configuration with planar arrangement of two ligand molecules around copper(II) ion and the anions occupying axial position¹⁹. The electronic spectra of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde/2-ethoxybenzaldehyde sulphato complexes of semicarbazone ligands show

Table 2 Magnetic moment and electronic spectral bands of copper(II) complexes

Complexes	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	ν_2 (cm ⁻¹) ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	ν_3 (cm ⁻¹) ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$
Cu(ebsc) ₂ Cl ₂	1.97	13375	15700
Cu(ebsc) ₂ Br ₂	1.92	13570	15705
Cu(ebsc) ₂ SO ₄	2.03	10870	-
Cu(ebsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.57	12570	15430
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	1.85	13398	15695
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ Br ₂	1.82	13600	17300
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ SO ₄	2.06	14405	18200
Cu(ebtsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.98	15200	18125
Cu(cbasc) ₂ Cl ₂	1.74	13570	16765
Cu(cbasc) ₂ Br ₂	2.00	14085	16850
Cu(cbasc) ₂ SO ₄	2.06	11290	-
Cu(cbasc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.59	14140	16980
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	1.98	14500	17270
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ Br ₂	2.08	15200	17800
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ SO ₄	2.04	13590	16280
Cu(cbtsc) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	2.02	15160	18200

only one intense absorption band at 10870 cm⁻¹ and 11290 cm⁻¹ respectively which may be assigned to ${}^2A_1 \rightarrow {}^2E''$ transition. These absorption bands are similar to earlier reported trigonal bipyramidal copper(II) complexes²⁰. Electronic spectra of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde/2-ethoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone sulphato complexes exhibit two absorption bands at 13590, 14405 cm⁻¹ and 16280, 18200 cm⁻¹ respectively. These absorption bands are characteristic for square pyramidal geometry²¹ of copper(II) complexes.

Based on elemental analysis, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies tetragonal planar configuration with two ligands around metal ion and anion occupying axial position have been proposed for complexes reported here except sulphato complexes. Five coordinated trigonal bipyramidal geometry has been suggested for semicarbazone sulphato complexes whereas square pyramidal geometry is proposed for thiosemicarbazone sulphato complexes under study.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of ligands :

The ligands 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone/

thiosemicarbazone (ebsc, ebtsc) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone (cbasc, cbtsc) were prepared according to the literature²² procedure by condensing 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde with semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide respectively and conformed by elemental analysis and IR spectral studies.

General method for synthesization of metal complexes :

A hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of metal salt (0.05 mol) was refluxed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the respective ligands (0.10 mol) keeping the molar ratio 1 : 2 for 3–4 h. The colored complexes were separated out on cooling the contents. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol, dried in the electric oven, analyzed and the data is reported in Table 1.

Physical and analytical measurements :

The analysis of C, H and N were done by micro analytical techniques. Metal contents were determined²³ by the precipitation of copper extract with dilute hydrochloric acid as cuprous thiocyanate. IR spectral data of the ligands and their complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR automatic recording spectrophotometer in potassium bromide. Electronic spectra of the complexes were scanned in ethanol on Shimadzu UV and Visible spectrophotometer 1601 C.P. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were determined by Guoy's method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant.

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